

A Combinatorial Model to Optimize Air Traffic Flow Management Problems*

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Abstract

In this paper we introduce a new 0-1 mathematical formulation for the Air Traffic Flow Management problem. The model is based on a 4D-graph, which allows us to consider the problem not as general combinatorial one, but as a set of shortest path problems with common capacity constraints, a fact that introduces several neat features. Among the decisions considered in the model are ground and air delays, changes in the speed of the aircraft and alternative routes. The proposed model, in comparison with the current state of the art, is shown to be an easy way to model different real complex situations (e.g., more realistic representation of costs and decisions involved, as well as dynamic sector configuration). The rapidity with which the computations are performed in this model shows the applicability of our proposal to the industry.

Keywords: Air Traffic Flow Management, 4D-graph, 0-1 mathematical optimization.

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1. Introduction

According to the International Air Transport Association (IATA) (IATA, 2016a,b), different regions of the world, such as Europe or the USA, are facing the problem of a saturated air traffic demand, i.e., the number of scheduled flights is sometimes larger than the capacity of the airspace and/or the airports. In order to avoid these congestion problems and, therefore, safety issues, some changes such as delays or alternative routes have to be proposed to the initial flight plan merely a few hours in advance (tactical decisions). The main consequences of these modifications include, on the one hand, an economic cost of billions of euros over the last years (IATA, 2013; Commission et al., 2016), and, on the other, a negative impact on the passengers' experiences (e.g.: in Europe, the quarterly average departure delay was about 12.5 minutes in 2016 (CODA, 2016)).

In order to mitigate these negative consequences more efficiently, the Air Traffic Management (ATM) is currently tackling through three different decision levels which are: Strategic, tactical and operational levels. The strategic level involves the scheduling of flights that will take place in a few months' time. At this level, some recent works by Bolić, Castelli, Corolli & Rigonat (2017)

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15 or Cai, Zhang, Xiao, Tang & Du (2017) try to schedule flights in such a way that the nominal
(theoretical) capacities of the system are also respected, therefore, when the flight plan is carried
out, less modifications need to be done. At the tactical decision level, which comprises the scope
of this work, the flight plan proposed at the strategic level is modified with updated information
20 about capacities so that it actually fulfills security restrictions. This problem is referred to as the
Air Traffic Flow Management Problem (ATFMP). Finally, at the operational level, the attention
is focused on collision avoidance, i.e., in order to guarantee a minimum separation between aircraft
during the flight plan, modifications in the route or speed of some aircraft can be performed by
air traffic controllers. Works in the literature which refer to this approach include those of Alonso-
Ayuso, Escudero & Martín-Campo (2016); Lehouillier, Nasri, Soumis, Desaulniers & Omer (2017).

25 With respect to the bibliography on the tactical decision level, Bertsimas & Patterson (1998)
is one of the most influential papers that has been published about this. The 0-1 mathematical
optimization model they proposed in that paper, based on the so-called step variables, considers
1) limits in the airspace, not only in the airports, 2) continued flights performed by the same
aircraft, and 3) decisions about assigning ground and air delays at a minimum cost. The proposed
30 formulation is so tight that most of the times it produces an integer solution when the problem
is relaxed. Regarding delay assignments, an interesting idea is presented in Lulli & Odoni (2007),
where the authors propose a model that obtains a *fair* distribution of the delays among the different
companies, ensuring that not all of the delays are transferred to only one company or one type of
flight.

35 In Bertsimas, Lulli & Odoni (2011), the authors extend the Bertsimas & Patterson (1998)
model by considering the rerouting and changes in the aircraft's speed. Equally, in Agustín,
Alonso-Ayuso, Escudero & Pizarro (2012a), the authors also extend the Bertsimas & Patterson
(1998) model, but, contrary to the previous work, pay attention to the flight network arcs instead
of the nodes. This model provides an improvement with respect to the previous ones: besides
40 ground and air delays, increases in the aircraft's speed, as well as flight cancellations, are explicitly
formulated and penalized. These modifications result in the so-called Air Traffic Flow Management
Rerouting Problem (ATFMRP). The computational experience presented shows that the majority
of the problems can be solved in the root of the Branch and Bound tree within a few minutes.

A different way in which the ATFMP has been addressed is through multicommodity flow
45 networks, i.e.: networks where each flight represents a commodity. Among the research carried
out in this area, we highlight the works by Bertsimas & Patterson (2000); Wei, Cao & Sun (2013);
Chen, Cao & Sun (2017). The difference between this approach and the previous works is that the
use of commodities does not specify which particular flights are assigned the proposed modifications
in the flight plans, thus a subsequent, normally complex procedure is needed to reconstruct the
50 flight routes.

Recently, various works such as those written by Diao & Chen (2018) or Akgunduz, Jaumard
& Moeini (2017) are trying to combine the operational and tactical levels in the same model,
incorporating collision avoidance constraints at the tactical decision level. The resulting models
are extremely complicated, even without considering all the complexities at the operational level;
55 therefore, only small instances can be solved. A remarkable characteristic of the second aforemen-
tioned model (also achieved by our model) is that it formulates the fuel-consumption-rate as a
function of speed (which is non constant).

Regarding the features of the works that have been reviewed, the main contribution of the
paper is the proposal of a new Combinatorial Optimization Model for the ATFMRP, which is more

60 versatile and allows a more realistic representation of some of the parameters of the problem, such
as, the costs/penalizations and the air sector configuration. Besides this fact, since the proposed
model is based on a 4D-graph, we can consider the problem at hand as a collection of shortest
path problems with common capacity constraints, which enlarges the range of solving strategies.
Moreover, a novel methodology, based on graph of conflicts to detect, beforehand, routes that will
65 be part of the optimal solution, is proposed.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we make a detailed description of
the ATFMRP. In Section 3, the proposed model is introduced and analyzed. First, the mathe-
matical optimization model is described in detail, then some extensions, to consider for instance
a dynamic air sector configuration, are presented. The Section concludes by giving an equivalent
70 representation of the proposed model as a collection of shortest path problems with common ca-
pacity constraints for which we present some preprocessing ideas to reduce the size of the problem.
In Section 4 the model is tested on different instances. Finally, in Section 5 the conclusions of the
work, as well as the future research lines, are presented.

2. Problem description

75 Let us consider a given set of airports \mathcal{K} , an airspace divided in a set \mathcal{J} of disjoint air sectors
and a set of flights \mathcal{F} departing from an airport, traversing different air sectors, and arriving to
an airport in the system. The planning horizon considered at this level is that one day, following
the most common approach in literature, it is discretized into a set of time periods (usually 5 to
15 minutes in length). Airports and air sectors have a limited capacity (the maximum number of
80 flights that can use this element at each time period). The goal is to guarantee that the capacity
of the airports and air sectors is not exceeded at any time, and when necessary, locate a new flight
plan for certain flights and minimize the global costs derived from these changes. The modifications
applied to the flight plans may include ground delays, air delays/advances in the arrivals at some
waypoints/airports or reroutings. An important feature within this problem is the existence of
85 continued flights, i.e., situations in which a flight must wait to take off until a previous one has
landed, usually because both are operated by the same aircraft. This fact causes an effect which
propagates decisions to the entire network of flights.

A flight plan determines the route for each flight, which is defined by the airports and waypoints
(air traffic control points at the boundary or inside each sector) and the scheduled time spent
90 passing through each of them. This definition leads us to represent the set of all possible alternative
routes of each flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$ by a directed network $\mathcal{G}_f = (\mathcal{N}_f, \mathcal{A}_f)$, where \mathcal{N}_f is the set of nodes
(airports and waypoints), and \mathcal{A}_f is the set of arcs that define the scheduled route, as well as
all of the possible alternative ones (see Agustín et al. (2012a) for more details). Let us consider
the illustrative example depicted in Figure 1. There are four air sectors (I, II, III and IV), three
95 airports (a_1 , a_2 and a_3) and eight way-points (w_1, \dots, w_8). Additionally, for each airport a_i we
consider two boundary nodes, $p(a_i)$ and $q(a_i)$, representing the entrance to and the exit from the
airport a_i , respectively. This example represents three flights, $f = 1$ departing from a_1 and going
to a_2 , $f = 2$ from a_2 to a_3 and $f = 3$ from a_1 to a_3 . Note that for the latter, two alternative routes
have been considered. Then $\mathcal{G}_3 = (\mathcal{N}_3, \mathcal{A}_3)$ is defined as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_3 &= \{a_1, q(a_1), w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5, p(a_3), a_3\}, \\ \mathcal{A}_3 &= \{(a_1, q(a_1)), (q(a_1), w_1), (w_1, w_2), (w_1, w_4), (w_2, w_3), (w_3, p(a_3)), (w_4, w_5), \\ &\quad (w_5, w_3), (p(a_3), a_3)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1: Illustrative example with three airports and four air sectors.

100 Each flight has a time period assigned for take-off from its departure airport and a scheduled number of time periods for traversing each arc in the network. Using this information, it is possible to obtain the scheduled arrival time at each node in the route (including the airport).

If, when using the scheduled flight plan for all flights in the network, the capacity at an airport or air-sector is violated, then, decisions to modify some of the flight plans have to be considered. For each flight f , the following decisions can be made: 1) Assigning ground delays, 2) Making changes in the speed of the aircraft while it traverses one or more arcs in its route, and 3) Selecting of an alternative route. In order to consider changes in the speed, let us denote by $\ell_{f,m,n}$ as the scheduled number of time periods that flight f spends traversing arc (m,n) . Then, delays and increases in the speed can be formulated by defining $\bar{\ell}_{f,m,n}$ and $\underline{\ell}_{f,m,n}$, upper and lower bounds, respectively, on the number of time periods that flight f can spend traversing arc (m,n) , for $(m,n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$ ($\underline{\ell}_{f,m,n} \leq \ell_{f,m,n} \leq \bar{\ell}_{f,m,n}$). Note: $\underline{\ell}_{f,m,n} = \bar{\ell}_{f,m,n} = 0$ for $(m,n) = (k_f^d, q(k_f^d))$ or $(m,n) = (p(k_f^a), k_f^a)$, where k_f^d and k_f^a are the departure and arrival airports for flight f , respectively.

The modification of the flight plans can combine ground delays, speed changes and rerouting, such that a flight may be affected by all of these measures simultaneously. Each decision has a cost associated to it and the goal of the problem is to obtain a feasible flight plan for each flight at a minimum cost without violating the capacity at any airport and/or air sector. Note that, since continued flights are operated by the same aircraft, all decisions concerning a continued flight can also affect its following flight; then, as exposed in Agustín et al. (2012a), if a flight is delayed, its following flight could suffer some delay. Therefore, a number of variables that account for the availability of the aircraft in the case of continued flights must be considered.

3. Problem formulation

3.1. Notation

Sets

125 $\mathcal{T} = \{1, \dots, T\}$, set of time periods.

\mathcal{K} , set of airports.

\mathcal{J} , set of air sectors.

\mathcal{F} , set of flights.

$\mathcal{C} = \{(f', f)\}$, set of continued flights such that f' is continued by flight f , with $f, f' \in \mathcal{F}$.

130 $\mathcal{F}_{\bar{p}} = \{f \in \mathcal{F} \mid \nexists f' \in \mathcal{F} : (f', f) \in \mathcal{C}\}$, set of flights without a predecessor.

\mathcal{N}_f , set of nodes that define all the available routes for flight f , $\forall f \in \mathcal{F}$.

$\mathcal{A}_f = \{(m, n) \mid m, n \in \mathcal{N}_f\}$, set of arcs that define all the available routes, i.e., traffic sequencing, for flight f , $\forall f \in \mathcal{F}$. The subset $\mathcal{A}_f^* \subset \mathcal{A}_f$ includes the arcs that define the scheduled route for flight f .

135 \mathcal{N}^j , set of nodes that belong to sector j , $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}$.

$\mathcal{A}_f^j = \{(m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f \mid m, n \in \mathcal{N}_f \cap \mathcal{N}^j\}$, set of arcs for flight f that belong to sector j , $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $j \in \mathcal{J}$.

$\Gamma_f^-(n) = \{m \mid (m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f\}$, set of nodes that head to node n for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$.

$\Gamma_f^+(n) = \{m \mid (n, m) \in \mathcal{A}_f\}$, set of nodes that have the node n as the tail for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$.

140 \mathcal{T}_f^n , set of feasible time periods for flight f to arrive at node n , $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $n \in \mathcal{N}_f$. Let us denote by T_f^n the last element in \mathcal{T}_f^n . See Wranas et al. (1994); Agustín (2011) for the details about this set computation

Parameters

$d_f \in \mathcal{T}$, scheduled departure time for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$.

145 $r_f \in \mathcal{T}$, scheduled arrival time to its destination for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$ when it follows its scheduled route.

$k_f^d \in \mathcal{K}$, departure airport for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$.

$q(k)$, node from the boundary of airport $k \in \mathcal{K}$ for the departure of any flight.

$k_f^a \in \mathcal{K}$, arrival airport for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$.

$p(k)$, node from the boundary of airport $k \in \mathcal{K}$ for the arrival of any flight.

150 $\ell_{f,m,n}$, scheduled travel time (i.e., number of time periods) for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$ to traverse arc $(m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$. Note 1: $\ell_{f,k_f^d,q(k_f^d)} = 0$ and $\ell_{f,p(k_f^a),k_f^a} = 0$. Note 2: $r_f = d_f + \sum_{(m,n) \in \mathcal{A}_f^*} \ell_{f,m,n}$.

$\underline{\ell}_{f,m,n}$ and $\bar{\ell}_{f,m,n}$, minimum and maximum travel time (i.e., number of time periods) that is allowed for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$ to traverse arc $(m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$, respectively. Note: $\underline{\ell}_{f,m,n} \leq \ell_{f,m,n} \leq \bar{\ell}_{f,m,n}$, for every arc in \mathcal{A}_f ; In particular, $\underline{\ell}_{f,k_f^d,q(k_f^d)} = \ell_{f,k_f^d,q(k_f^d)} = \bar{\ell}_{f,k_f^d,q(k_f^d)} = 0$ and $\underline{\ell}_{f,p(k_f^a),k_f^a} = \ell_{f,p(k_f^a),k_f^a} = \bar{\ell}_{f,p(k_f^a),k_f^a} = 0$.

$s_{f',f}$, turnaround time, i.e: time needed for preparing flight f after the arrival of f' , $(f', f) \in \mathcal{C}$. Note: it is assumed that $r_{f'} + s_{f',f} \leq d_f$.

D_k^t , departure capacity of airport $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at time $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

R_k^t , arrival capacity of airport $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at time $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

160 C_k^t , joint departure and arrival capacity of airport $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at time $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

S_j^t , capacity of sector $j \in \mathcal{J}$ at time $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

Additional sets and parameters

Using the previous notation, the following sets and parameters can be introduced:

- 165 • $\mathcal{T}_f^{m,n} = \{(t_1, t_2) \mid t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_f^m, t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_f^n, \underline{\ell}_{f,m,n} \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq \bar{\ell}_{f,m,n}\}$, set of all feasible pair time combinations for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$ such that f is travelling through the arc (m, n) from t_1 until t_2 , for $(m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$. Note: since $\underline{\ell}_{f,m,n} = \bar{\ell}_{f,m,n} = 0$ for $(m, n) = (k_f^d, q(k_f^d))$ and $(m, n) = (p(k_f^a), k_f^a)$, then $\mathcal{T}_f^{m,n} = \{(t, t) \mid t \in \mathcal{T}_f^n\}$, for those special arcs.
- $c_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2}$, penalization for flight $f \in \mathcal{F}$ for using arc $(m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$ if f arrives to node m at t_1 and to node n at t_2 , for $(t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n}$.

170 Note that for every arc $(m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$ in the air space, $c_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2}$ represents the penalization of speed decreases of the aircraft for $t_2 - t_1 > \ell_{f,m,n}$, whereas for $t_2 - t_1 < \ell_{f,m,n}$ represents the penalization of speed increases. The rerouting cost can be considered by penalizing arcs in $\mathcal{A}_f \setminus \mathcal{A}_f^*$. For the special arcs $(p(k_f^a), k_f^a)$ and $(k_f^d, q(k_f^d))$, $c_{f,k_f^d,q(k_f^d)}^{t,t}$ represents the penalization of a ground delay of $t - d_f$ time periods and $c_{f,p(k_f^a),k_f^a}^{t,t}$ represents the penalization of late (for $t > r_f$) or early (for $t < r_f$) arrivals.

The existence of continued flights has a propagation effect in the network. In particular, for each pair $(f', f) \in \mathcal{C}$, two different situations may appear: 1) Flight f' arrives on time (or, in some cases, with a small delay), then flight f plan is not affected; 2) Flight f' arrives late so, flight f should be delayed. Now, let us consider the following sets associated to each pair $(f', f) \in \mathcal{C}$:

- 180 • For each $t \in \mathcal{T}_f^{k_f^d}$, $\mathcal{T}_{f',f}^t = \{t' \mid t' \in \mathcal{T}_{f'}^{k_{f'}^a} \text{ such that } t = \max\{d_f, t' + s_{f',f}\}\}$. If flight f' arrives in one of these periods, then t is the first period at which the aircraft assigned to f is ready to take off.

For the sake of clarity in the definition of sets $\mathcal{T}_{f',f}^t$, let us consider a pair of flights $(f', f) \in \mathcal{C}$ such that f' can arrive at $\mathcal{T}_{f'}^{k_{f'}^a} = \{5, 6, 7, 8\}$, f can depart at $\mathcal{T}_f^{k_f^d} = \{7, 8, 9\}$, but waiting a minimum of $s_{f',f} = 1$ time period for preparing the aircraft. Thus, if flight f' arrives at $t' = 5$, flight f must wait until $t = 7$ before departing; therefore $\mathcal{T}_{f',f}^7 = \{5, 6\}$, $\mathcal{T}_{f',f}^8 = \{7\}$, $\mathcal{T}_{f',f}^9 = \{8\}$. Note that $\{\mathcal{T}_{f',f}^t, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^{k_f^d}\}$ defines a partition of $\mathcal{T}_{f'}^{k_{f'}^a}$.

Variables

190 $z_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2} = 1$, if flight f leaves node m at time t_1 and arrives at node n at time t_2 , and 0 otherwise,
 $\forall f \in \mathcal{F}, (m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f, (t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n}$

$y_f^t = 1$, if the aircraft that operates flight f is ready for taking off at (the beginning of) time t , and 0 otherwise, $\forall f \in \mathcal{F}, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^{k_f^d}$.

195 **Remark 3.1.** We assume that for flights $f \in \mathcal{F}_{\bar{p}}$, the aircraft is always ready for departing at d_f (i.e., $y_f^{d_f} = 1$), while for subsequent flights, the aircraft is not ready from the beginning, being only available if the previous flight has arrived well in advance (i.e., $y_f^{d_f} = 0, \forall f \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{F}_{\bar{p}}$).

3.2. Mathematical formulation

Objective function

$$\min \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \sum_{(m,n) \in \mathcal{A}_f} \sum_{(t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n}} C_{f,m,n}^{t_1, t_2} z_{f,m,n}^{t_1, t_2}. \quad (1)$$

Capacity constraints

$$\sum_{\substack{f \in \mathcal{F}: \\ \{k_f^d = k, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^k\}}} z_{f,k,q(k)}^{t,t} \leq D_k^t, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{\substack{f \in \mathcal{F}: \\ \{k_f^a = k, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^k\}}} z_{f,p(k),k}^{t,t} \leq R_k^t, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{\substack{f \in \mathcal{F}: \\ \{k_f^d = k, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^k\}}} z_{f,k,q(k)}^{t,t} + \sum_{\substack{f \in \mathcal{F}: \\ \{k_f^a = k, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^k\}}} z_{f,p(k),k}^{t,t} \leq C_k^t, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \sum_{(m,n) \in \mathcal{A}_f^j} \sum_{\substack{(t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n}: \\ t_1 \leq t < t_2}} z_{f,m,n}^{t_1, t_2} \leq S_j^t, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (5)$$

Flight structure constraints

$$y_f^{d_f} = 1, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}_{\bar{p}}, \quad (6)$$

$$y_f^t = y_f^{t+1} + z_{f,k_f^d, q(k_f^d)}^{t,t}, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}_{\bar{p}}, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^{k_f^d} \setminus \{T_f^{k_f^d}\}, \quad (7)$$

$$y_f^t = z_{f,k_f^d, q(k_f^d)}^{t,t}, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}_{\bar{p}}, t = T_f^{k_f^d}, \quad (8)$$

$$y_f^{d_f} = 0, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{F}_{\bar{p}}, \quad (9)$$

$$y_f^t + \sum_{t' \in \mathcal{T}_{f',f}^t} z_{f',p(k_{f'}^a), k_{f'}^a}^{t',t'} = y_f^{t+1} + z_{f,k_f^d, q(k_f^d)}^{t,t}, \quad \forall (f', f) \in \mathcal{C}, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^{k_f^d} \setminus \{T_f^{k_f^d}\}, \quad (10)$$

$$y_f^t + \sum_{t' \in \mathcal{T}_{f',f}^t} z_{f',p(k_{f'}^a), k_{f'}^a}^{t',t'} = z_{f,k_f^d, q(k_f^d)}^{t,t}, \quad \forall (f', f) \in \mathcal{C}, t = T_f^{k_f^d}, \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{m \in \Gamma^-(n)} \sum_{(t', t) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n}} z_{f,m,n}^{t',t} = \sum_{m' \in \Gamma^+(n)} \sum_{(t, t') \in \mathcal{T}_f^{n,m'}} z_{f,n,m'}^{t,t'}, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}, n \in \mathcal{N}_f \setminus \{k_f^d, k_f^a\}, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^n. \quad (12)$$

$$z_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2} \in \{0,1\}, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}, (m,n) \in \mathcal{A}_f, (t_1,t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n}, \quad (13)$$

$$y_f^t \in \{0,1\}, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}, t \in \mathcal{T}_f^{k_f^d}, \quad (14)$$

The objective function (1) accounts for the operation costs, including decisions about delays, rerouting or changes in the speed. Constraints (2)-(5) ensure that the capacity is respected at all times. Constraints (6) state that all flights without a predecessor must have an aircraft assigned to a flight ready within the first time period in which they have scheduled to depart; constraints (7) state that if a flight has its aircraft ready at time period t , then it can be scheduled for departing at that time period or delayed one additional period; constraints (8) force the flight to depart if its aircraft is still ready at the beginning of the last time period it can depart. Constraints (9) state that a flight with a predecessor does not have its own aircraft ready to depart within the first time period in which it has scheduled to depart (since it is operated by the same aircraft as its predecessor, see Remark 3.1). Constraints (10)-(11) are similar to constraints (7)–(8) but for flight f with a predecessor f' . In these cases, the right-hand side of each restriction takes into account that flight f can depart (or be delayed one additional time period) at time period t if its aircraft is ready from the previous time period ($y_f^t = 1$) or its predecessor flight f' has arrived well enough in advance ($\sum_{t' \in \mathcal{T}_{f',f}^t} z_{f',p(k_{f'}^a),k_{f'}^a}^{t',t} = 1$). Constraints (12) guarantee that once the aircraft reaches waypoint n , then it leaves it at the same time period.

3.3. The objective function

The priority aim of these air traffic management models is to find flight plans so that the capacities of the different elements (airports and air sector) are not exceeded. This is achieved by proposing a set of constraints that adequately define a feasible region. Moreover, objective function coefficients should be oriented towards choosing a solution that does not differ excessively from the initial planning and that, in addition, does so in the most balanced way possible. The solutions that are sought must: 1) prefer ground delays to air delays; 2) propose speed changes as smooth as possible; 3) propose alternative routes when the original route is not available; 4) penalize delayed arrivals. In addition, these proposals should be such that changes are fairly distributed between different flights (for example, a solution in which two flights have a delay of one period is preferable to a solution in which a single flight concentrates two periods of delay). One of the advantages of the proposed model over the previous models in the literature, Bertsimas et al. (2011) and Agustín et al. (2012a), is precisely the flexibility to fix the coefficients in the objective function in order to take those facts into account. Notice that, since each variable $z_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2}$ contains information about the time leaving the tail node m and reaching the head node n , these variables determine the speed at which the aircraft traverses arc (m,n) . This implies that we can penalize changes in the speed in a non-linear way which is what actually happens in reality. To better understand this consider the following example: let us consider two aircraft, one flying from node m to node n , and another flying from m' to n' . Imagine that the scheduled travel time for the first route is 20 minutes, while the second one is 25 minutes. Now consider that both aircraft must be delayed 5 minutes in their respective routes. If we penalized delays based on this quantity (as the current state of the art does), both cases would have the same cost even though they should not because the first case

requires a reduction in the speed of 25%, while in the second requires one of 20%. Thanks to our variables we know the percentage of reduction beforehand, therefore we can establish penalizations based on this non-linear quantity while maintaining linearity in our model. As far as we know, the only work which also incorporates this idea is (Akgunduz et al., 2017). To be specific, we have considered the following penalization structure.

Let us consider the arc that joins the node (m, t_1) with (n, t_2) : if the variable associated to this arc takes the value 1, then the corresponding flight reaches waypoint m at time period t_1 and leaves it to waypoint n , arriving to it at time period t_2 . The penalization $c_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2}$ is such that:

- If $m = k_f^d$ (Departure/ground delay penalization). Based on Bertsimas et al. (2011), we use $c_{f,k_f^d,q(k_f^d)}^{t,t} = c_g |t - d_f|^{1+\epsilon_1}$, where c_g is a ground delay penalization. For $\epsilon_1 > 0$ this is a convex and superlinear penalization, looking for a better distribution of the delays between several flights (the penalization is greater for one flight delayed two periods and another none than for two flights delayed one period each)
- If $n = k_f^a$ (arrival airport): $c_{f,p(k_f^a),k_f^a}^{t,t} = c_a |t - a_f|^{1+\epsilon_2}$. Arrival delay penalization (see Bertsimas et al. (2011)). As in the previous case, it seeks to distribute small delays in arrivals among several flights as opposed to concentrating large delays on a few flights.
- In all other cases (arcs corresponding to airspace): $c_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2} = c_r + c_v \frac{|t_2 - t_1 - \ell_{m,n}|^{1+\epsilon_3}}{\ell_{m,n}}$. This penalization includes several elements:
 - c_r is a penalization for the use of arcs which do not belong to the main route, so that $c_r = 0$ for arcs in the main route and $c_r > 0$ for the rest.
 - As in departure and arrival delays penalization, ϵ_3 seeks to penalize the concentration of speed changes in a few arcs, as opposed to a more balanced distribution between several arcs.
 - And, on the other hand, by dividing the penalization by the time initially scheduled to traverse that arc, the length of the arc is also taken into account: the less the scheduled time to cross an arc, the greater the penalization for increasing the flight time by one unit, since the change in speed is greater. This element tends to avoid great velocity changes in the short arcs.
 - Finally, coefficient c_v is a constant to penalize velocity changes.

Note that, while penalization for delays in arrivals and departures are common in the literature, penalization at intermediate points is not straightforward. In fact, very few papers consider it. In particular Agustín et al. (2012a) penalize the deviations in the arrivals to each waypoint using a linear function but without taking into account the length of the arc (it does not penalize the change in speed, but the delay in the arrival to the waypoint).

In general, since ground delays are preferred to air delays it seems to be recommendable to set $c_g < c_v$. Figure 2 shows the impact of the different values of the ϵ parameter. The left side picture represents the penalization assigned to departure (for $c_g = 1$) and arrival delays (for $c_a = 1$); the right side picture represents the penalization assigned to the increment in the time (that corresponds to a velocity change) spent for a flight in traversing an arc for $\ell_{f,m,n} = 2$, $c_r = 0$ and $c_v = 1$. Note that $\epsilon = 0$ corresponds to the linear case.

Figure 2: Illustration of the penalization function

3.4. Model extension

Usually, sectors are defined taking into account the maximum number of flights that air traffic controllers working in a single sector can safely manage. Initially, the airspace is divided into so-called 'elementary' sectors, which can be assembled into larger units called 'collapsed' sectors. A partition of the entire airspace, defined by a specific combination of elementary and/or collapsed sectors, is called sector configuration (see Baumgartner (2007)). Therefore, along the planning horizon, different sector configurations can be used in order to adapt the nominal capacity of the sectors to the expected traffic. Unlike previous models in the literature that use a fixed sector configuration during the whole planning horizon, the model that we present here allows for a dynamic one.

This is because our model considers flight routes as sequences of waypoints not necessarily associated to air sectors boundaries (some of them can lie in the interior), making the flight structure independent of the air sector configuration. As an example, let us suppose that in the instance illustrated in Fig. 1, instead of having a static airspace division in four air sectors, $\{I, II, III, IV\}$, the Air Traffic Control service considers that, from a given time period t^* , sector II must be split into two different sectors, say II_a and II_b (see Fig. 3). Then, the set of sectors is $\mathcal{J} = \{I, II, II_a, II_b, III, IV\}$ that, obviously, is not a partition of the airspace. But considering $\mathcal{J}_t = \{I, II, III, IV\}$ for $t < t^*$ and $\mathcal{J}_t = \{I, II_a, II_b, III, IV\}$ for $t \geq t^*$, \mathcal{J}_t defines a sector configuration for each t . Now, w_2 is an exit waypoint from sector II_a and an entering point to sector II_b .

For our model to capture this new dynamic air-sector disposition, the only information needed is the set of sectors that define the partition at each time period and the entrance and exit waypoints for each sector (note that these points can be inner points in other sector configuration). Then, due to the independent flight and sector configuration mentioned before, the only change required in model (1)–(14) is the domain of constraints (5), that, for each $t \in \mathcal{T}$, must be $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}_t$, instead of $j \in \mathcal{J}$.

3.5. An alternative model representation

The previous model (1)–(14), thanks to indexing variables by arcs $(m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$ and by the time leaving n and reaching m , allows to represent flight routes in a 4D-graph structure. That is, a graph $\tilde{\mathcal{G}} = (\tilde{\mathcal{N}}, \tilde{\mathcal{A}})$, where each node $n \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}$ represents a position in the space and the time in which that position can be reached, and where each arc $a \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ corresponds to a particular decision

Figure 3: Illustration of dynamic sector configuration

Figure 4: Example of 3D flight plan.

variable. Subsequently, it allows us to exploit this particular structure of the model in order to be solved more efficiently.

310 For instance, for a given flight f , graph $\mathcal{G} = (A_f, \mathcal{N}_f)$ shown in Figure 4 represents the set of two available routes that f can follow departing from airport k_1 to airport k_3 ¹. The figure shows, for each arc, the minimum, the scheduled and the maximum number of time periods that flight f needs for traversing it. Using this information and considering that, for example, the flight is scheduled to take off at $t = 1$, and that the maximum ground delay is one time period, it is possible to build the 4D-graph $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_f = (\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_f, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_f)$ represented in Figure 5. In that graph, each circled-node $nt \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_f$ has associated the node $n \in \mathcal{N}_f$ and a time period $t \in \mathcal{T}_f^n$.

There exists an arc from node mt_1 to node nt_2 in the following two cases:

- If $m \neq n$ and it is feasible for flight f to go from node $m \in \mathcal{N}_f$ to node $n \in \mathcal{N}_f$, departing at t_1 and arriving at t_2 . It is not difficult to see that there is a one-to-one correspondence between the arcs $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_f$ of this form and the z -variables in model (1)–(14). To be specific, arc (mt_1, nt_2) is associated with variable $z_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2}$, for all $(m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$, $(t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n}$.
- If $m = n = k_f^d$, $t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_f^{k_f^d} \setminus \{T_f^{k_f^d}\}$ and $t_2 = t_1 + 1$. These arcs (the vertical one in the figure) represent one period ground delay of the flight. Notice that there is also a one-to-one correspondence between these arcs and the y -variables in model (1)–(14): each arc represents

¹Due to aesthetic reasons, when drawing the text inside the nodes, instead of using $q(k_1)$ and $p(k_3)$, we will use k_1^o and k_3^i respectively.

Figure 5: 4D-graph example

325 a one-time period ground delay for the flight, so the aircraft is ready at the beginning of next time period.

In Figure 5, can also be appreciated that the graph includes the (auxiliary) diagonal node n_ℓ , which represents the end of aircraft operations and which is linked to every arrival airport node by double-line arcs. These arcs have no decision variables associated.

330 Note that there is a one-to-one correspondence between each possible flight plan in the example and each path of the 4D-graph from k_11 (in general, $k_f^d d_f$) to n_ℓ . In particular, the initial scheduled plan is represented using bold arcs.

335 With regard to the costs, since each non-dashed arcs in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_f$ has a correspondence with a decision variable in model (1)–(14), a cost \tilde{c}_a for each arc $a = (mt_1, nt_2)$ in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_f$ is assigned such that $\tilde{c}_a = c_{f,m,n}^{t_1,t_2}$, for $(m,n) \in \mathcal{A}_f$, $(t_1,t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n}$. The cost for the double-line arcs is set to 0. As a consequence, the path from $k_1, 1$ to n_ℓ at minimum cost represents the cheapest (presumably the original) flight plan for flight f .

340 This graph can be extended to cases where an aircraft operates several continued flights. We can define a graph $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s = (\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_s, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s)$ where $s \in \mathcal{S} = \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{S}|\}$ stands for the s -th aircraft. Let us consider the example of two continued flights shown in Figure 6. The nodes and arcs defining each flight remain as in the one-flight 4D-graph. The two flights are linked by new double-line arcs.

Figure 6: 4D-graph for two continued flights

These new arcs represent the transition from the first flight to the second one (in the example, a turnaround time $s_{f',f} = 1$ has been considered). A node associated to the arrival airport of the first flight is linked to a node associated to the departure airport of the second flight under the following condition: the time period associated to the latter is the earlier time period in which the second flight can depart, once the first flight has arrived at the time period associated to the former node. Note that those new double-line arcs do not represent any decision, therefore, they do not have any variable associated. In fact, the 4D-graph can be shrunk by merging every set of nodes connected by those double-line arcs in just one node. As shown in Figure 5, each path from k_{11} to n^ℓ represents a specific flight plan set for the flights operated by the aircraft.

From the previous figures, it is clear that using this representation based on the 4D-graphs $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s = (\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_s, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s)$, $s \in \mathcal{S}$, the ATFMRP can be formulated as a set of shortest path problems (one per each aircraft $s \in \mathcal{S}$) with common capacity constraints. To that end, let us previously introduce the following notation:

\mathcal{F}_s , the set of flights f that belong to graph $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s$, $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $f \in \mathcal{F}$. Notice that $\{\mathcal{F}_s | s \in \mathcal{S}\}$ defines a partition of \mathcal{F} . Note also that there exists a unique first flight $f_0^s \in \mathcal{F}_s \cap \mathcal{F}_{\bar{p}}$ and a unique last flight $f_\ell^s \in \mathcal{F}_s$ operated by aircraft s .

$\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{s,k,t}^{\text{dep}} = \{a = (kt, q(k)t) \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s | f \in \mathcal{F}_s : k = k_f^d, (t, t) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{k,q(k)}\}$, set of arcs referred to time period t which connect the departure's airport nodes of flights in \mathcal{F}_s , $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

$\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{s,k,t}^{\text{arri}} = \{a = (p(k)t, kt) \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s | f \in \mathcal{F}_s : k = k_f^a, (t, t) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{p(k),k}\}$, set of arcs referred to time period t which connect the arrival's airport nodes of flights in \mathcal{F}_s , $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

$\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{s,j,t}^{\text{sec}} = \{a = (mt_1, nt_2) \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s \mid f \in \mathcal{F}_s : (m, n) \in \mathcal{A}_f^j, (t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_f^{m,n} : t_1 \leq t < t_2\}$, set of arcs referred to time period t which belong to sector j of the s -th graph, $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $j \in \mathcal{J}$, $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

Hence, the ATFMRP can be formulated as a set of multiple shortest path problems (one per each group of flights operated by the same aircraft $s \in \mathcal{S}$) with common capacity constraints:

$$\min \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s} \tilde{c}_{s,a} \rho_{s,a}, \quad (15)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{a \in \Lambda^+(n)} \rho_{s,a} - \sum_{a \in \Lambda^-(n)} \rho_{s,a} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n = k_{f_0^s}^d d_{f_0^s}, \\ -1, & \text{if } n = n_\ell^s, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, n \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_s \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{s,k,t}^{\text{dep}}} \rho_{s,a} \leq D_k^t, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{s,k,t}^{\text{arri}}} \rho_{s,a} \leq R_k^t, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{a_1 \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{s,k,t}^{\text{arri}}} \rho_{s,a_1} + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{a_2 \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{s,k,t}^{\text{dep}}} \rho_{s,a_2} \leq C_k^t, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{s,j,t}^{\text{sec}}} \rho_{s,a} \leq S_j^t, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (20)$$

$$\rho_{s,a} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, a \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s, \quad (21)$$

where $\rho_{s,a}$ is a binary variable that takes value 1 if arc $a \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s$ belongs to the minimum path in graph $s \in \mathcal{S}$ and 0 otherwise, and $\Lambda^+(n)$ and $\Lambda^-(n)$ are the sets of out-going and in-going arcs for node $n \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_s$ respectively.

Proposition 3.1. *Models (1)–(14) and (15)–(21) are equivalent.*

Proof. The proof follows straightforward from the network construction made before. \square

As a direct consequence, it can be concluded that the ATFMRP belongs to the class NP-complete, since the constrained shortest path problem is NP-complete (see Appendix B in Ahuja, Magnanti & Orlin (1993)).

Note that, as it is well known, all extreme points of the feasible region defined by constraints (16) are integer, since the matrix associated to these constraints is totally unimodular. Furthermore, if each variable has non-zero coefficients in, at most, one of these constraints, model (15)–(21) corresponds to a transportation model with added partial sum conditions which does not have variables in common for any pair of conditions, and therefore it can be reduced to a standard transportation problem (see Dantzig (1963, Ch. 18-3)). Then, in such case, the LP relaxation of the problem (15)–(21) always has at least one integer solution.

3.6. Graph of conflicts

To reduce the size of the mathematical formulation, we propose a methodology based on the construction of a conflict graph. By using this graph, the problem could eventually be split in disjoint subproblems that could be solved independently. Furthermore, in some cases, the size of the problem can be reduced by removing some alternative routes or even identifying when the main route of a flight has no conflict with any other flight and, therefore, can be fixed and removed from the problem.

The cornerstone of this procedure is that capacity constraints define conflicts between aircraft, i.e., there is a conflict between each pair of aircraft with non-zero coefficients in the same capacity constraint (since they may not be able to occupy the same sector at the same time). We can distinguish among three kinds of conflicts: those that occur between the main routes of the aircraft, those which involve the main route of one of the aircraft and a secondary route of the other one, and those that occur between secondary routes of the aircraft. We will represent these conflicts through a multigraph $\mathcal{H} = \{\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{M}\}$, where \mathcal{S} is the set of aircraft and \mathcal{M} is the set of arcs, such that $(s, s') \in \mathcal{M}$ if aircraft s and s' are involved in a potential capacity conflict. We say that two aircraft are involved in a potential conflict if, for any of their feasible flight plans, they share the same air sector at the same time period. In terms of the 4D-graph, aircraft s and s' have a potential conflict if there are at least one arc in $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s$ and one arc in $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_{s'}$ such that both have a non-zero coefficient in the same capacity constraint. To use this idea for reducing the size of the problem, let us first introduce the following elements:

$\mathcal{A}_s^* \subseteq \mathcal{A}_s$, subset of arcs belonging to \mathcal{A}_s that define the main route, $s \in \mathcal{S}$.

\mathcal{RC} , set of index of the capacity constraints. Note that if it can be proven, using some preprocessing process, that a capacity constraint is redundant (i.e., the maximum number of aircraft that can eventually be flying through the constraint's associated sector and time period is not greater than its capacity), then, the constraint index can be removed from \mathcal{RC} .

\mathcal{RC}_i , set of arcs in $\cup_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s$ with non-zero coefficients in constraint $i \in \mathcal{RC}$.

The set of arcs \mathcal{M} is the union of three disjoint sets: \mathcal{M}^{pp} , \mathcal{M}^{ps} and \mathcal{M}^{ss} , which represent each of the three considered kinds of conflicts:

\mathcal{M}^{pp} , arcs connecting two aircraft (nodes) that have at least one conflict in their main routes. Formally, $(s, s'), (s', s) \in \mathcal{M}^{pp} \Leftrightarrow \exists i \in \mathcal{RC}$ such that $\mathcal{RC}_i \cap \mathcal{A}_s^* \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{RC}_i \cap \mathcal{A}_{s'}^* \neq \emptyset$, for $s, s' \in \mathcal{S}$, $s \neq s'$.

\mathcal{M}^{ps} , arcs connecting two aircraft that have at least one conflict in the main route of the first of them with an alternative route of the other one. Mathematically, $(s, s') \in \mathcal{M}^{ps} \Leftrightarrow \exists i \in \mathcal{RC}$ such that $\mathcal{RC}_i \cap \mathcal{A}_s^* \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{RC}_i \cap \mathcal{A}_{s'} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{s'}^* \neq \emptyset$, for $s, s' \in \mathcal{S}$, $s \neq s'$. Note that, in general, $(s, s') \not\Leftarrow (s', s)$.

\mathcal{M}^{ss} , arcs connecting two aircraft that have at least one conflict in their alternative routes. Mathematically, $(s, s'), (s', s) \in \mathcal{M}^{ss} \Leftrightarrow \exists i \in \mathcal{RC}$ such that $\mathcal{RC}_i \cap \mathcal{A}_s \setminus \mathcal{A}_s^* \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{RC}_i \cap \mathcal{A}_{s'} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{s'}^* \neq \emptyset$, for $s, s' \in \mathcal{S}$, $s \neq s'$.

We can take advantage of constructing that multigraph by means of the following results, which allow to decompose the original problem into independent subproblems, and/or reduce its size.

Proposition 3.2. *Let $\mathcal{H} = \{\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{M}\}$ be the multigraph of conflicts associated to a given ATFMRP problem. Then, it follows:*

- 425 (i) *Model (15)–(21) for the ATFMRP can be solved by optimizing independent subproblems, each of them associated to one connected component of graph \mathcal{H} .*
- (ii) *For each singleton connected component of \mathcal{H} , the main route of all flights operated by this aircraft is part of the optimal solution.*
- (iii) *If for an aircraft $s \in \mathcal{S} \nexists s' \in \mathcal{S} : (s, s') \in \mathcal{M}$, then the main route of all flights operated by s is part of the optimal solution.*
- 430 (iv) *If for a connected component of $\mathcal{H} \nexists s, s' \in \mathcal{S} : (s, s') \in \mathcal{M}^{pp}$, then the main routes of all flights operated by aircraft of that component are part of the optimal solution.*

Proof. The proof is straightforward, taking into account that only capacity constraints (17)–(20) have non-zero coefficients in more than one aircraft. Thus, by construction, if two aircraft belong to different connected components, none of the flights operated by these aircraft can use the same sector/airport at the same time-period in any of their feasible 4D-routes, and therefore (i) and 435 (ii) hold. By construction, if condition (iii) holds, the main route of aircraft s is free of conflicts and, thus, it can be used in the optimal solution. Condition (iv) is very restrictive, since it implies that there is no conflict between the main routes of that related component. In such a case, it is impossible that there exists a violation of capacity constraints when the flights are using their 440 main routes and, therefore, the main route of all the involved flights can be included in the optimal solution. \square

4. Computational experience

The proposed model has been tested by using six data sets (named BLO1, BLO2, BLO3, C01, C02 and C03) already used in the literature by Bertsimas et al. (2011); Agustín et al. (2012a). In 445 the original paper, the C0i data sets consider flight cancellations, so we have removed it. In all the data sets, delays and rerouting are considered, but not the increases in speed. Both data sets have alternative routes for some flights that are occasionally shorter than the main one, so a flight might depart with a delay, but still land on the scheduled time. The size of the data sets can be found in Table 1. The headings are as follows: $|\mathcal{K}|$, number of airports; $|\mathcal{J}|$, number of air sectors; 450 $|\mathcal{F}|$, number of flights; $|A_r|$, number of alternative routes; $|\mathcal{T}|$ number of time periods; and $|\mathcal{C}|$ the number of continued flights. Note that in BLO instances, the airspace is subdivided into sectors of equal dimensions that form a grid and the length of each time period is set such that it corresponds to the minimum amount of time needed to traverse a sector (the same for all the flights and for all the sectors) while C0i instances were created assuming a length of 5 minutes per time period.

455 To carry out the computational experience we have used a computer with 16 GB of RAM and Intel processor i7-7700HQ 2.80GHz, with a Linux Mint 19 operating system. We have also employed Gurobi 8.1 inside a C++ framework.

We have tested four different scenarios for each instance. The scenarios have been created by using the following ideas in Bertsimas et al. (2011): First of all, a base scenario is created 460 by assigning to each element (air sectors, arrival airports and departure airports) the minimum capacity needed for all flights departing and arriving on time using their scheduled flight plan. Note that we have assigned the same capacity to all air-sectors, in addition, the same departure and arrival capacities have been assigned to all departure and arrival airports, respectively. Afterwards,

Table 1: Dimensions of the data sets.

Set	$ \mathcal{K} $	$ \mathcal{J} $	$ \mathcal{F} $	$ A_r $	$ \mathcal{T} $	$ \mathcal{C} $
C01	40	30	1054	1710	49	535
C02	40	45	1330	2330	60	706
C03	45	39	1545	2622	60	809
BLO1	4	44	812	3182	88	105
BLO2	20	112	3196	5108	117	1016
BLO3	30	144	6475	14901	119	2742

Table 2: Dimensions of the instances.

Instance	#Variables	#Constraints
C01	87918	52224
C02	151166	88078
C03	156526	91180
BLO1	1653585	271992
BLO2	4033583	749334
BLO3	7979391	1366532

to stress a little bit more the model, the capacity of each sector has been randomly reduced
465 between 10% and 30%. The joint capacity of airports has been established as 75% of the sum
of the corresponding individual capacities. As in Bertsimas et al. (2011), different scenarios have
been created simulating the effect of a front of bad weather, which moves across the region of
interest along a certain direction, causing a capacity reduction in subsets of sectors over time. The
reduction of capacity affects three sectors at a time, for five consecutive time periods. Beginning
470 with some set of three sectors, we reduce their capacity for five periods; after those five time
periods, the impact in the capacity reduction is moved to another three contiguous sectors for
acting during other five time periods. This capacity reduction method is repeated until reaching
the last time period of the instance. The reductions have been established to 90%, 80%, 70% and
60%, leading to a total of 24 scenarios. For the sake of clarity, we have also include the results for
475 the scenario in which no weather penalization is applied. The penalization parameters described
in Section 3.3 have been set equal to $\epsilon_1 = 0.25$, $\epsilon_2 = 0.75$, $\epsilon_3 = 0.50$, $c_g = 1$, $c_a = 1$, $c_v = 4$
and $c_r = 2(t_2 - t_1 - \ell_{m,n})$. With this configuration the penalization for alternative route is large
enough so that, unless necessary to avoid a conflict, it is preferable to force the flight to land a few
minutes late. In addition, the penalization coefficient c_v for air delays is set to 4 to avoid air delays
480 when there is an alternative with ground delays. Afterwards, the penalization of each arc has been
randomly modified $\pm 10\%$. Notice that the penalization for using alternative routes is fairly large,
so these will be used just to avoid conflicts or when the arrival delay becomes excessively large.

The dimensions of each of the instances are in Table 2, where heading #Variables stands for
the number of (binary) variables and heading #Constraints for the number of flow and capacity
485 constraints. The density of the matrix of constraints (the number of non-zero elements divided by
the product of the number of variables by constraints) for all of the instances is less than 0.01%.
In addition, when formulating the graph of conflicts, we do not obtain independent subproblems,
but we manage to reduce the number of variables and constraints by up to 0.11% and 5.37%

Table 3: Computational results.

Instance	Z_{LP}	Z_{IP}	GAP	t (s)	nn
C01-100	94.61	94.61	0.00%	3.92	0
C01-90	198.21	198.26	0.02%	5.08	1
C01-80	363.88	363.88	0.00%	4.13	0
C01-70	565.52	565.52	0.00%	4.44	0
C01-60	898.40	898.81	0.05%	6.03	1
C02-100	46.25	46.25	0.00%	6.24	0
C02-90	52.15	52.15	0.00%	6.50	0
C02-80	63.14	63.14	0.00%	6.41	0
C02-70	87.17	87.17	0.00%	6.49	0
C02-60	132.79	132.79	0.00%	6.59	0
C03-100	183.28	184.36	0.59%	12.61	31
C03-90	205.58	206.63	0.51%	12.98	29
C03-80	263.32	264.31	0.38%	13.43	43
C03-70	468.04	470.01	0.42%	17.50	835
C03-60	1046.38	1048.44	0.20%	14.61	84
BLO1-100	1255.31	1255.31	0.00%	83.19	0
BLO1-90	1374.83	1375.09	0.02%	100.72	1
BLO1-80	1551.62	1551.84	0.01%	126.14	1
BLO1-70	1838.56	1838.99	0.02%	115.37	1
BLO1-60	2299.30	2300.42	0.05%	116.50	1
BLO2-100	2806.54	2807.07	0.02%	195.93	1
BLO2-90	2875.18	2875.97	0.03%	197.13	1
BLO2-80	3010.27	3011.73	0.05%	222.70	1
BLO2-70	3595.09	3595.26	0.00%	199.84	1
BLO2-60	4925.86	4925.96	0.00%	191.21	1
BLO3-100	8130.21	8141.1	0.13%	831.031	1
BLO3-90	9103.68	9118.47	0.16%	943.192	7
BLO3-80	10593.93	10613	0.18%	860.931	1
BLO3-70	12882.14	12907.1	0.19%	858.105	1
BLO3-60	17090.99	17126.5	0.21%	741.852	1

respectively.

490 In Table 3 the main computational results are presented. The headings of the table are: Z_{LP} for the optimal value of the linear relaxation of the problem, Z_{IP} for the optimal objective of the original problem, GAP stands for the integrality gap defined as $100 \frac{Z_{IP} - Z_{LP}}{Z_{LP}}$, t for the last time (in seconds) including the graph of conflicts computation, and nn for the number of nodes explored in the Branch and Cut process².

495 Finally, Table 4 shows the modifications applied to the original flight plan. The headings of the table are: FNI for the number of flights with a modification in the original flight plan, FS for number of flights with a change in speed (usually air delay), FLD for the number of flights with late departure (due to ground delays), FLA for the number of flights with late arrival (due to air and ground delays or, rerouting) and FR for the number of flights rerouted.

500 It can be shown that, due to the structure of the penalization, ground delay is the most frequent decision among the three that can be made (ground delay, speed change and rerouting). In addition, it is easy to see how the modification of a flight plan by any of these three decisions does not necessarily translate into a delay in arrival, since the simultaneous application of two or

²For all the cases, the optimum solution is achieved and, when solving them without the idea of the graph of conflicts, the time employed by Gurobi is similar to the total time presented in the table. That is to say, for these instances, there is barely any difference when using or not the graph of conflicts.

Table 4: Flight plans

Instance	<i>FNI</i>	<i>FS</i>	<i>FLD</i>	<i>FLA</i>	<i>FR</i>
C01-100	53	13	28	49	4
C01-90	92	24	46	82	10
C01-80	129	40	62	109	22
C01-70	171	56	81	143	34
C01-60	214	66	108	169	53
C02-100	25	7	17	20	5
C02-90	28	10	16	24	4
C02-80	35	11	19	31	4
C02-70	53	12	26	47	6
C02-60	69	19	35	61	9
C03-100	104	22	55	91	15
C03-90	107	23	56	91	17
C03-80	136	28	71	121	17
C03-70	188	51	104	158	33
C03-60	260	75	146	210	60
BLO1-100	118	44	106	92	63
BLO1-90	147	44	135	114	74
BLO1-80	170	46	157	127	90
BLO1-70	213	68	185	160	106
BLO1-60	236	99	198	187	110
BLO2-100	255	17	255	30	231
BLO2-90	288	25	288	37	258
BLO2-80	308	32	308	66	262
BLO2-70	454	71	454	133	356
BLO2-60	594	119	594	289	404
BLO3-100	837	90	825	418	444
BLO3-90	968	181	944	554	469
BLO3-80	1022	273	990	608	496
BLO3-70	1087	340	1046	671	525
BLO3-60	1208	387	1143	794	547

505 more of these measures compensates their effects. In particular, in the BLO examples it is common to find solutions with shorter alternative routes that allow compensating for delays in departure.

5. Conclusions and future lines of research

We have presented a new optimization model for the Air Traffic Flow Management Problem which allows for a better representation of penalizations as well as for taking into consideration the dynamic structure of the air-sectors configuration by means of intermediate way-points. We have shown an equivalent representation of the problem -based on a 4D-graph- as a set shortest path problems with common capacity constraints. This feature enables us to enlarge the range of solving strategies, which will be specially important for our future research plans. Besides the model and its properties, we have also introduced a novel idea to reduce the size and complexity of the problem. The graph of conflicts and the propositions presented allow to determine beforehand when the main route of a flight will be part of the optimal solution.

Among our future research plans, we aim to investigate new ways of solving the problem by applying decomposition techniques (i.e., Lagrangean Decomposition) to exploit the good properties of the shortest path problems.

520 The model that we have presented assumes that all parameters are known in advance, but, in particular, capacities are weather-dependent and, therefore, can vary along the time horizon. Following the ideas of previously written works (see Agustín et al. (2012b), among others), we are

planning to extend the model to consider uncertainty in the capacities, modeled via a representative scenario tree. Although the computational experience shows that the instances can be solved within a reasonable computing time, making the proposal applicable to the industry in the deterministic case, good decomposition methods will be needed for tackling the resolution of the huge and complex mathematical formulations that appear in this context.

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